

12th International Conference of Control Theory and Computer Modelling (CTCM 2026)

August 22 ~ 23, 2026, Dubai, UAE

<https://csen2026.org/ctcm/index>

Scope

12th International Conference of Control Theory and Computer Modelling (CTCM 2026) is a forum for presenting new advances and research results in the fields of Control Theory and Computer Modelling. The conference will bring together leading researchers, engineers and scientists in the domain of interest from around the world in these areas.

Topics of interest

- Control theory
- Linear and nonlinear control systems
- Optimization and optimal control
- Robust control
- Adaptive control
- Digital control
- Feedback control
- Sliding mode control
- Soft computing and control
- Process control and instrumentation
- Fault detection and isolation
- Model predictive control
- Stochastic control and filtering
- Systems and automation
- Networked control systems
- Hybrid systems
- Agriculture, environment, health applications
- Industry, military, space applications
- Scientific computing
- Embedded systems
- Real-time issues
- Neural networks and fuzzy logic
- Genetic algorithms and evolutionary computing
- Numerical analysis and scientific computing
- System identification and control
- Computer modelling
- Mathematical modelling

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **May 24, 2026**.

Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology](#) (CS & IT) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **CTCM 2026**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [The International Journal of Control Theory and Computer Modelling \(IJCTCM\)](#)
- [International Journal of Information Technology, Control and Automation \(IJITCA\)](#)
- [International Journal of Chaos, Control, Modelling and Simulation \(IJCCMS\)](#)
- [The International Journal of Information Technology, Modeling and Computing \(IJITMC\)](#)

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : May 24, 2026**
- Authors Notification : June 13, 2026
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : June 20, 2026

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : ctcm@csen2026.org or conferencectcm@yahoo.com